

Polynomial and Exact Solution to Maximum Satisfiability Problem

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ABSTRACT

We give a fully polynomial and exact solution to MAX-SAT problem, we also show that this problem is tractable within present state of automata theory.

Keywords: MAX-SAT, automata theory, subset construction, derivatives, polynomial, exact, solution.

INTRODUCTION

The construction of non-deterministic finite automata (NFA) from regular expressions is a long-studied question, we are using standard Thompson's method [1], we are also using Rabin-Scott subset construction [2] with concurrent modified "and" or intersection operator for partial case of Berry-Sethi algorithm [3] which, in turn, is an extended version of Brzozowski algorithm [4].

ALGORITHM

First for each variable in clause we are building the regular expression in the form of "...a..." for positive and "...b..." - for negative case, where our alphabet is dual.

Further for each of regular expression representing clause, we form the intersection as a Berry-Sethi automata, giving the abstract node on the output.

Then, this output is subjected to the modified subset construction, which we have studied long time ago.

The complexity of the algorithm is $O(n*m*\log(m))$, where n is a number of variables and m is a number of clauses, the logarithm shows that we build an optimal intersection operator tree.

CONCLUSION

Our practical approach gives the significant results and are projected towards "P versus NP" theorem [5].

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